

Sensorimotor adaptation and its transfer to motor command is altered in high autistic tendency

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Background and objectives

Theories of *Autism Spectrum Disorder* suggest that the integration between prior knowledge and sensory evidence may be affected in ASD¹.

Here, we tested whether the buildup of weak priors affects the transfer of adaptation-induced changes in the motor command to other sensorimotor circuitry in healthy adults with various degrees of Autistic Traits.

Results

Displacing the target 3° inward leads to a shortened saccade amplitude and influences target localization in both groups.

High AQ failed to use the adapted efferent copy to remap the pre-saccadic target position to its predicted target location when the target was displaced 3° outward

Methods

Saccade adaptation Visual localization

Pupil change before saccade and visual localization

Larger pupil dilation accompanies motor preparation before saccade and localization trials, in low AQ participants

Pupil change after saccade and visual localization

Increased pupil size in high AQ suggest a "surprise"³ reaction to target displacement and to visual localization.

Conclusions

- Prior knowledge about the position of the displaced target is used for saccade planning;
- The use of error signals for the internal recalibration of the sensory-motor system is altered in AQ phenotype together with the transfer of the recalibration to visual space perception (only for outward adaptation);
- Pupil size provides valid indicator qualities for ongoing cortical processes;
- Priors are important for basic level sensory-motor control and could play a role in higher level of processing, such as predicting social behavior.